

How Microscale Flow and Vapor Transport Shape New Particle Formation and Growth

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Abstract

Accurate simulation of atmospheric new particle formation (NPF) remains limited because large-scale models cannot resolve aerosol processes at fine spatial scales, while detailed microphysics models assume spatially homogeneous conditions. Here we use a high-resolution three-dimensional multiphysics modeling framework (3D-ICAM) to quantify how environmental heterogeneity governs NPF dynamics at meter scales. Simulations performed at 10 m resolution across contrasting emission conditions reveal that spatial gradients in wind fields and precursor vapor convergence substantially modify local nucleation intensity, particle growth rates, and size distribution structure. Even under weak winds ($< 1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), the model reproduces spatially complex nucleation “hotspots” and evolving banana-plot signatures that cannot emerge under homogeneous conditions. Comparisons with equivalent box model simulations show that environmental variability alone can shift predicted growth rates by up to 37%, indicating that flow and dilution dynamics can amplify or dampen chemically driven nucleation signals, which homogeneous box models cannot distinguish from purely chemical effects. These results demonstrate that meter-scale environmental structure

exerts first-order control on urban NPF and must be resolved to accurately interpret field observations and predict particle number budgets.

Synopsis

This work shows that microscale flow and vapor transport critically control atmospheric particle formation, improving understanding relevant to air quality and climate.

Introduction

New particle formation (NPF) is a major source of atmospheric aerosol particles and plays a critical role in shaping cloud properties, radiative forcing, and air quality.¹ It refers to the formation of nanometer-scale molecular clusters that grow into particles capable of acting as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN).² NPF contributes a substantial fraction of global CCN, reaching up to 80% in some regions,³ and influences both background particle populations and pollution episodes.⁴ In urban settings, freshly formed particles interact with local emissions and boundary-layer dynamics, whereas in remote or marine environments NPF is frequently the dominant particle source. Although chemical pathways involved in nucleation are increasingly well understood, the environmental controls that modulate how these pathways manifest in real atmospheric settings remain incompletely characterized, particularly in heterogeneous urban landscapes.⁵ Understanding the interplay between chemistry, meteorology, and emissions is therefore essential for improving air quality forecasts and reducing uncertainties in aerosol–climate interactions.

Over the past two decades, advances in observational techniques have greatly improved the mechanistic understanding of NPF. Field campaigns employing condensation particle counters (CPCs), scanning mobility particle sizers (SMPS), and chemical ionization mass spectrometry (CIMS) have characterized precursor vapors such as sulfuric acid, ammonia, and amines with molecular-level detail.⁶ Long-term measurements at ground-based networks,

including the SMEAR stations in Finland, have quantified NPF frequency, seasonality, and growth rates across diverse environments.^{5,7-11} Machine learning and image-recognition approaches have improved consistency in event classification,^{5,12,13} while high-resolution mass spectrometry has revealed the composition of early clusters, including acid–base complexes and highly oxygenated organic molecules.³ These advances have provided unprecedented chemical and temporal detail, but they also underscore the need for models that can interpret observations within environmentally realistic, spatially structured settings.

Despite extensive observational progress, current modeling frameworks struggle to resolve the spatial and temporal complexity of NPF in real environments. Global climate models (GCMs) operate at coarse spatial resolutions and represent aerosols with a small number of size modes.^{14,15} Regional climate and large-eddy simulation models achieve finer spatial resolution but still rely on simplified aerosol microphysics that cannot represent early-stage cluster formation. These frameworks are valuable for assessing large-scale aerosol–climate interactions, yet they are not designed to capture microscale variability relevant for NPF in polluted or topographically complex regions.³ In contrast, zero-dimensional (0D) box models^{4,16} and one-dimensional parcel models^{17,18} resolve detailed chemistry and microphysics using tens to hundreds of size bins, but they assume spatial homogeneity and therefore cannot represent flow-driven vapor accumulation, dilution, or horizontal gradients. This mismatch between highly resolved observational datasets and spatially coarse or homogeneous modeling frameworks limits our ability to interpret NPF dynamics in real-world conditions.

To address this gap, we apply a high-resolution three-dimensional multiphysics modeling tool (3D-ICAM) to investigate how environmental heterogeneity modulates NPF. 3D-ICAM resolves particle dynamics at 10 m resolution and couples size-resolved aerosol microphysics with evolving meteorological fields through two-way feedbacks. The framework integrates a computational fluid dynamics module for wind, temperature, humidity, and emissions; an aerosol chemistry and microphysics module that simulates nucleation, condensation, coagulation, and deposition; and a particle transport module that advects and diffuses size-resolved

particle distributions. This structure enables mechanistic investigation of how flow structures and environmental gradients shape NPF behavior. These are features absent from both coarse-resolution climate models and non-spatial box models. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to examine NPF at meter-scale (~ 10 m) resolution in a fully coupled 3D domain, enabling direct exploration of how environmental processes amplify, suppress, or modify chemically driven nucleation and growth.

Methodology

We apply a Three-Dimensional Integrated Chemistry–Aerosol–Microphysics model (3D-ICAM) to simulate size-resolved new particle formation (NPF) with full spatial and temporal resolution in an urban-scale domain. The model resolves coupled fluid dynamics, gas–aerosol chemistry, and particle microphysics to capture how evolving environmental structure influences nucleation and early growth.

Simulations are conducted in a 10^9 m³ domain (1 km \times 1 km \times 1 km) discretized at 10 m resolution. 3D-ICAM outputs three-dimensional fields of particle number concentration ($dN/d \log D_p$), nucleation-mode particle abundance ($D_p \leq 3$ nm), and size-dependent growth rates throughout the domain.

Model Structure

3D-ICAM consists of three dynamically coupled components (Fig. 1). The **Air3D** module solves the atmospheric flow, temperature, humidity, and precursor vapor fields using a buoyancy-coupled computational fluid dynamics (CFD) framework. The **AMChem** module simulates gas-phase chemistry and aerosol microphysics, including cluster formation, nucleation, condensation, coagulation, and deposition across 80 size bins. The **Aero3D** module transports aerosol populations by advection and turbulent diffusion.

At each time step, Air3D provides updated meteorological and vapor fields to AMChem,

which computes nucleation and growth rates. Aero3D then transports the size-resolved aerosols, and resulting concentrations feed back to Air3D and AMChem. This fully coupled loop allows changes in flow, dilution, and vapor convergence to directly influence particle formation and vice versa.

Figure 1: Schematic of the 3D-ICAM model architecture, showing the coupling between Air3D (flow and meteorology), AMChem (aerosol chemistry and microphysics), and Aero3D (size-resolved transport) modules. The model uses meteorological and emissions data as input and simulates size-resolved new particle formation (NPF) with full spatial and temporal resolution.

Air3D: Atmospheric Flow and Scalar Transport

Air3D solves the conservation equations for mass, momentum, energy, and scalar species using a finite-volume approach with a standard $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence closure. The model includes buoyancy effects, turbulent mixing, and three-dimensional advection–diffusion of precursor vapors. These fields determine local saturation ratios and thereby regulate nucleation and condensational growth.

Complete governing equations, numerical discretization details, and turbulence parameterizations are provided in the Supporting Information (Section S1) and follow the formulation of Ghosh et al.¹⁹.

AMChem: Aerosol Microphysics and Chemistry

The AMChem module simulates aerosol dynamics using a sectional representation of particle sizes. It is built on the general dynamic equation framework of Ghosh et al.¹⁹ and includes nucleation, coagulation, condensation, and deposition processes.

Nucleation is represented using a cluster-kinetic scheme based on the four-acid–four-base (A_4B_4) formulation of Brean et al.⁴, which describes the formation of thermodynamically stable clusters from sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) and a generic base (B) such as dimethylamine (DMA), monoethanolamine (MEA), or NH_3 . The parameterization accounts for acid–base collision rates, cluster evaporation, and losses of vapors to the pre-existing condensation sink. The full expression for the nucleation rate and all associated parameters are given in the Supporting Information (Section S2).

Coagulation is treated by combining five physical kernels representing different collision pathways: Brownian motion, convective Brownian diffusion enhancement, gravitational collection, turbulent inertial motion, and turbulent shear. The kernels include slip-flow corrections and, where relevant, van der Waals interactions, following Vohra et al.²⁰ and Ghosh et al.¹⁹. Condensational growth is driven by H_2SO_4 vapor and is computed using a modified expression based on Laakso et al.²¹, neglecting charge effects but retaining size dependence and transition-regime corrections. Size-resolved dry deposition to the ground is implemented using size-dependent deposition velocities that account for gravitational settling and near-surface turbulent transport, following Ghosh et al.¹⁹, Vohra et al.²⁰.

All microphysical processes are evaluated in 80 logarithmically spaced size bins spanning 1–5000 nm. AMChem is advanced in time using a semi-implicit numerical scheme designed to conserve aerosol mass and number and to maintain numerical stability at high particle number concentrations.²² Full mathematical formulations and numerical details are provided in the Supporting Information (Section S2).

Aero3D: Size-Resolved Particle Transport

The Aero3D module simulates the three-dimensional transport and dispersion of aerosols across the domain. It evolves the number concentration of particles in each size bin as a function of space and time, driven by advection and turbulent diffusion using the flow and turbulence fields provided by Air3D.

Effective particle diffusivities combine Brownian diffusion (computed via the Stokes–Einstein relation for each size bin) and turbulent eddy diffusion derived from the local turbulence characteristics. This formulation allows Aero3D to represent size-dependent spreading of freshly formed particles and the development of spatial gradients in nucleation-mode and larger particles. The underlying transport equation, numerical solution method, and treatment of coupling with AMChem are described in the Supporting Information (Section S3), following the approach of Ghosh et al.¹⁹.

Model Setup and Numerical Configuration

The 3D-ICAM simulations are performed in a cubic computational domain of volume 10^9 m^3 ($1000 \text{ m} \times 1000 \text{ m} \times 1000 \text{ m}$), discretized using a uniform 10 m grid in all three spatial directions (Fig. 2). Each simulation is run for 24 h with a fixed time step of 1 min.

To evaluate how the spatial configuration of emissions influences NPF, we consider four emission geometries: one point source (PS) and three line sources (LS200, LS300, LS500). The point source is located at the center of the horizontal domain, 30 m above ground level. The three line sources form square perimeters at 30 m height, centered at the domain midpoint, with side lengths of 200, 300, and 500 m, respectively. The 30 m height is chosen to represent typical rooftop-level or stack emissions in an urban neighborhood.²³ These configurations allow us to isolate the effect of emission extent and geometry on nucleation intensity, growth rates, and spatial patterns of particle number concentrations under otherwise identical meteorological drivers.

Figure 2: Computational domain used in the 3D-ICAM simulations. The domain is a cube of volume 10^9 m^3 ($1000 \text{ m} \times 1000 \text{ m} \times 1000 \text{ m}$), discretized using a uniform structured grid with 10^3 m^3 resolution. Emission configurations include a point source (PS, green) at the center of the domain at 30 m height and three line sources (LS200, pink; LS300, blue; LS500, yellow) forming square perimeters at 30 m height with side lengths of 200, 300, and 500 m, respectively.

Aerosol particle sizes are represented using 80 logarithmically spaced bins from 1 to 5000 nm. Key initial and boundary conditions are summarized in Table 1, with additional details provided in the Supporting Information (Section S4).

The model is implemented in MATLAB R2023b and parallelized using GPU acceleration (NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060 Ti) to make meter-scale simulations over 10^6 grid cells computationally feasible. The semi-implicit treatment of aerosol microphysics and the implicit flow solver together enable numerically stable, fully coupled 24 h simulations for each emission scenario. Additional numerical performance details are provided in the Supporting Information (Section S4).

Meteorological and Emissions Forcing

Time-varying meteorological forcing is based on measurements reported by.⁶ Hourly temperature, relative humidity, and horizontal wind speed and direction are used as time-dependent

Table 1: Summary of initial and boundary conditions for the 3D-ICAM simulations.

Parameter	Value
Domain size	1000 m \times 1000 m \times 1000 m
Grid resolution	10 m (uniform)
Total number of grid cells	10^6
Simulation duration	24 h
Time step	1 min
Numerical integration	Implicit (Air3D); semi-implicit (AMChem, Aero3D)
Temperature	5–25 °C, time-varying, spatially uniform ⁶
Horizontal wind field	Hourly values from, ⁶ nudged each hour
Vertical velocity	Constant 0.1 m s ⁻¹
Relative humidity	35–90% over 24 h ⁶
Emitted species	H ₂ SO ₄ , DMA, MEA, NH ₃
Base emissions	DMA/MEA/NH ₃ : 10^7 molecules cm ⁻³ h ⁻¹ (constant) ⁴
H ₂ SO ₄ input	Time-varying concentration profile, peak $\sim 10^7$ molecules cm ⁻³ ²⁴
Initial aerosol distribution	Log-normal, mode 170 nm, 20–1000 nm, total 10^5 m ⁻³ ⁶
Aerosol size representation	80 logarithmically spaced bins (1–5000 nm)
Hygroscopicity (κ)	0 (non-hygroscopic)
Particle density	1.83 g cm ⁻³
Nucleation scheme	$J_{A_4B_4}$ for H ₂ SO ₄ –base clusters ⁴

boundary conditions. Temperature and relative humidity are assumed spatially homogeneous but evolve in time according to the observed diurnal cycle (SI Fig. S4.2a). Wind velocity fields are prescribed at the lateral boundaries and nudged hourly toward the observed wind vectors to maintain realistic advection patterns (SI Fig. S4.2b).

Gas-phase precursors include H₂SO₄ and three bases: DMA, MEA, and NH₃. Base emission rates are held constant at 10^7 molecules cm⁻³ h⁻¹, following Brean et al.⁴. H₂SO₄ concentrations are prescribed as a time-varying profile with daytime maxima of order 10^7 molecules cm⁻³, based on Cai et al.²⁴. The diurnal evolution of H₂SO₄ and the resulting nucleation rates for each base combination are shown in SI Fig. S4.1.

Results and discussion

Wind flow field

Figure 3: Three-dimensional wind velocity field simulated by the Air3D module at four time points during the 24-hour simulation: (a) 6 hours, (b) 12 hours, (c) 18 hours, and (d) 24 hours. Wind speed (in m s^{-1}) is represented by the color scale, while black arrows indicate the direction of the velocity vectors at each cubic grid point.

Figure 3 presents the three-dimensional wind velocity field simulated by the Air3D module at four time points throughout the 24-hour simulation: 6 hours (panel a), 12 hours (panel b), 18 hours (panel c), and 24 hours (panel d). The background color shading represents wind speed (in m s^{-1}), while the overlaid black arrows show the local wind direction at each grid point within the domain. The wind profile in Air3D was driven by time-varying

meteorological data measured at an urban site in New Delhi, India, as reported by.⁶ These measurements, taken at 10 m above ground level, indicated calm conditions with horizontal wind speeds typically below 0.5 m s^{-1} . To simulate this, a parabolic vertical wind profile was initialized from 10 m height upward, consistent with the measurement level, while a weak vertical updraft of 0.1 m s^{-1} was imposed and a free-slip condition was applied at the top (Z) boundary to permit unimpeded vertical flow development. Hourly wind velocity values were nudged at the lateral (X and Y) boundaries of the simulation domain. Wind rose diagram for the 24-hour simulation period used as input is shown in the Supporting Information Fig. S4.2 (b).

Despite the low wind velocities imposed at the domain boundaries, the simulated flow field in Figure 3 reveals substantial internal variability that develops over time. The black arrows indicate complex directional patterns even at early time points, with horizontal winds near the ground moving in different directions across the domain, a clear signature of low-level shear. As the simulation progresses, the color shading shows the emergence of horizontally layered regions with distinct wind speeds, particularly in the mid to upper levels of the domain (e.g., at 12 and 18 hr), indicating vertical stratification. By 24 hr, localized zones with swirling or misaligned flow vectors appear, suggesting the onset of vertical mixing and turbulence-like behavior. These features arise from buoyancy-driven convection and interactions between spatial gradients in temperature, pressure, and velocity, which are dynamically resolved by the Air3D module using the $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence scheme. The ability of Air3D to reproduce such evolving 3D structures under calm, urban conditions underscores its value in capturing how air parcels move and interact in space. Even in the absence of strong wind, the internal flow remains highly structured, and a homogeneous velocity field does not emerge.

Aerosol number concentrations

Figure 4: Spatio-temporal evolution of the total number concentration of nucleation-mode particles (1 – 3 nm), denoted by N_{1-3} (in m^{-3}), at four time points from the start of simulation: (a) 6 hours, (b) 12 hours, (c) 18 hours, and (d) 24 hours. Each row corresponds to a different initial emission geometry case: (i) point source (PS), (ii) line source with 200 m side length (LS200), (iii) line source with 300 m side length (LS300), and (iv) line source with 500 m side length (LS500).

Figure 4 shows the spatio-temporal evolution of the total number concentration of nucleation-mode particles (N_{1-3}) over the 24-hour simulation period for the four different emission geometries. In the point source (PS) case (top row), nucleation is initially (at 6 hr) confined to a small vertical column directly above the source, reflecting localized acid-base cluster formation under calm flow conditions. As time progresses, only limited horizontal spread is observed, and by 18–24 hr, N_{1-3} sharply declines, reflecting particle growth out of the 1–

3 nm size range due to condensation and coagulation, as supported by the N_{1-10} distributions shown in the Supporting Information Fig. S5.1.

In contrast, the line source configurations (LS200, LS300, LS500) display wider spatial distributions of N_{1-3} at early times, corresponding to greater total precursor emissions distributed over larger areas. However, even within these extended geometries, nucleation is not spatially uniform. Instead, localized nucleation "hotspots" emerge along the emission perimeters, driven by the interaction of vapor concentration fields and the evolving wind velocity structure (Figure 3). As the simulation advances, the spatial distribution of N_{1-3} in each case evolves further, shaped not just by emission patterns but also by advection and turbulent diffusion. This is particularly evident between 12–24 hr, when subtle differences in local wind direction and shear lead to asymmetric particle distributions, even under weak background wind conditions.

These results highlight a key departure from prevailing assumptions in many recent NPF studies. While it is widely recognized that NPF is governed by gas-phase chemistry and aerosol microphysics, such as acid-base nucleation and condensational growth, several works ignore the role of atmospheric dynamics. For instance, Brean et al.⁴ assert that transport plays a relatively minor role in affecting the size distribution. Similarly, Zhao et al.³ emphasize precursor availability and chemical pathways while treating atmospheric transport primarily as a source of uncertainty, rather than a mechanistic driver of NPF. Even in more data-driven approaches, such as the deep learning framework developed by Su et al.⁵ to classify NPF event types, meteorological or spatial information is not incorporated implicitly assuming that size distribution patterns alone are sufficient for interpretation. In contrast, our simulations show that environmental dynamics, particularly the local wind field structure, can significantly influence the spatio-temporal characteristics of NPF, even when chemistry, emissions, and microphysics are similar.

Figure 4 reveals strong spatial heterogeneity in N_{1-3} that cannot be explained by emissions alone. This becomes particularly clear when examining different time points for the

same emission geometry. In the LS300 case, for example, precursor emissions and microphysical conditions remain fixed throughout the simulation, yet the spatial distribution of N_{1-3} changes markedly over time. At 6 hr (panel a (iii)), localized hotspots exceeding 10^{10} m^{-3} appear along segments of the emission perimeter, while neighboring regions remain below 10^7 m^{-3} . At 18 and 24 hr (panels c and d (iii)), the nucleation field evolves further, shifting in position and intensity, with some regions decreasing to as low as 10^2 m^{-3} , despite no changes to emissions or chemistry. These changes align with the evolving wind field shown in Figure 3, where directional shear and stratification influence vapor accumulation and mixing. The persistence of elevated N_{1-10} concentrations in Fig. S5.1 confirms that the observed declines in N_{1-3} are primarily due to particle growth beyond the 3 nm threshold rather than loss. Similar trends in spatio-temporal evolution are observed across all emission cases (PS, LS200, LS500), reinforcing that environmental transport is a dominant factor shaping the structure of NPF. Together, these findings directly contradict the assumption that NPF can be adequately represented as a spatially homogeneous process. They demonstrate that even under weak wind conditions ($< 0.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), environmental dynamics shape when and where new particles form.

Growth rate

Figure 5: Three-dimensional distribution of particle growth rate (in nm/hr) for the 1 – 25 nm size range, evaluated over the duration of NPF events within the 24-hour simulation period, under four different emission geometry cases: (a) point source (PS); line sources with (b) 200 m side length (LS200), (c) 300 m side length (LS300), and (d) 500 m side length (LS500).

Figure 5 shows the three-dimensional distribution of particle growth rates within the 1–25 nm size range (GR_{1-25}), calculated over the duration of NPF events in each simulation. Despite identical chemical and microphysical processes across the domain, the resulting growth rates vary substantially in space, with values exceeding 40 nm hr^{-1} (dark red) in some localized regions while remaining below 10 nm hr^{-1} (dark blue) elsewhere. This spatial heterogeneity is evident across all emission geometries but is most pronounced in the LS200 and LS300 cases (panels b and c), where vapor retention and localized mixing support enhanced growth over extended volumes. In contrast, the LS500 case (panel d) shows growth that is more

spatially confined, likely due to greater dilution of vapor precursors and enhanced dispersion over the larger perimeter. The point source case (panel a) also reveals significant variability. Despite its compact emission source, adjacent regions within the domain exhibit growth rates below 5 nm hr^{-1} (dark blue), near 10 nm hr^{-1} (light blue), and above 45 nm hr^{-1} (dark red), a span of nearly an order of magnitude, highlighting the fine-scale sensitivity of growth to local environmental conditions.

To better understand the size dependence of these patterns, we also evaluate growth rates in three separate diameter ranges: $1 - 3 \text{ nm}$, $3 - 10 \text{ nm}$, and $10 - 25 \text{ nm}$, shown in Supporting Information Figs. S5.2, S5.3, and S5.4, respectively. In the early growth regime ($1-3 \text{ nm}$; Fig. S5.2), growth rates are generally low (typically below 5 nm hr^{-1}) and more spatially patchy. This is consistent with strong competition between condensation and scavenging losses during the initial growth stages, and suggests that particle survival through this bottleneck depends critically on micro-environmental conditions. The intermediate range ($3-10 \text{ nm}$; Fig. S5.3), shows more structured gradients but with maximum growth rate values rarely exceeding 10 nm hr^{-1} . These rates are sufficient to enable particle progression into the climatically relevant Aitken mode under favorable vapor availability, but still reflect significant spatial variability induced by flow features. In contrast, the $10-25 \text{ nm}$ range (Fig. S5.4) exhibits consistently higher growth rates (up to $30-40 \text{ nm hr}^{-1}$ in some cases), and smoother spatial patterns. This reflects a regime where particle loss rates are lower and condensational growth becomes more efficient and less sensitive to local gradients.

These growth patterns reflect the influence of the evolving wind field, as shown in Figure 3, which drives local gradients in vapor availability through directional shear, stratification, and transport. Vapor-rich pockets and low-wind regions likely serve as convergence zones where condensing species accumulate, enhancing both condensation and coagulation processes. The fact that particle growth varies significantly across the domain, even under fixed emissions and chemistry, reinforces the conclusion from Figure 4 that environmental dynamics, not just chemical pathways, play a decisive role in shaping aerosol evolution. Furthermore,

spatial alignment between elevated N_{1-3} regions and high growth zones suggests that particle formation and growth are tightly coupled to the flow field and not uniformly distributed, as often assumed.

These findings have broader implications for interpreting and modeling atmospheric particle growth rates. Particularly in connection with the persistent "growth rate mystery", where observed growth rates substantially exceed predictions from condensation-based models, even when constrained by detailed gas-phase measurements and advanced volatility basis set frameworks. For example,²⁵ show that while modeled growth rates can match observations under specific springtime conditions, they tend to be overestimated or underestimated in summer and urban environments. Similarly,²⁶ demonstrate that widely used parameterizations fail to reproduce the full diversity of observed sub-10 nm growth events across seasons and settings. While these discrepancies are typically attributed to missing chemical pathways or particle-phase limitations, our results suggest that environmental dynamics, such as advection, vapor convergence, and turbulent mixing, may also play a decisive role. The spatial variability in growth rates shown here, despite fixed precursor chemistry, reveals how flow-driven heterogeneity can amplify or suppress particle growth at the microscale. This indicates that atmospheric transport and local environmental structure may constitute a previously underappreciated contributor to the growth rate discrepancy and should be more explicitly considered in both model development and interpretation of field data.

Impact of 3D environment in simulations

To isolate the role of spatial dynamics in NPF, we compared the output of the full 3D-ICAM model to a 0D version of the simulation that includes only the chemistry and aerosol microphysics module (AMChem), without the CFD or particle transport components. This 0D configuration is equivalent to a box model and represents a spatially homogeneous environment subject only to time-varying precursor emissions and meteorological conditions. It is consistent in structure with other state-of-the-art 0D frameworks^{4,16}. For direct comparison,

we extracted time series output from the central grid point of the 3D domain at 30 m height and compared it with the 0D model output under identical input conditions.

Figure 6: Time evolution of particle number size distributions ($\log_{10}(dN/d \log D_p)$) at the central grid point (30 m height) for the 0D reference model (panel a) and the four 3D emission cases (panels b–e). Color contours represent the logarithmic particle number concentration. The black line indicates the geometric mean diameter of the fitted nucleation mode (NPF mode) over time, obtained from mode fitting of the particle number size distributions.

Figure 6 shows the evolution of particle number size distributions over a 24-hour period at the central grid point (30 m height) for the 0D reference model (panel a) and the four 3D emission scenarios (panels b–e). Banana-shaped particle number size distribution plots are a well-known feature of atmospheric NPF events, displaying a characteristic upward-curving trajectory in $dN/d \log D_p$ as particles form and grow from nanometer sizes. In all panels, the black line indicates the geometric mean diameter of the fitted nucleation mode (NPF mode) over time, obtained from lognormal mode fitting of the particle number size distributions. In the 0D model, which includes chemistry and microphysics but excludes transport and environmental structure, the banana shape is smooth, continuous, and symmetric, closely resembling the well-known Ia-type event⁵.

In contrast, the 3D simulations produce banana shapes that vary substantially across

emission geometries. The PS case (panel b) exhibits two distinct growth episodes: an initial burst in the early hours and a second later in the day. This split pattern results from local flow structures periodically displacing larger particles away from the observation point, reducing the local condensation sink and allowing NPF to restart. Such multi-burst behavior is absent in the 0D model, where the condensation sink remains uniformly high once particles have formed.

The LS200 and LS300 cases (panels c and d) show intermittent growth with sharper transitions in the geometric mean diameter. Their larger spatial extent and distributed emission sources enable vapors to accumulate intermittently at the observation point, as evolving wind fields advect precursor-rich air parcels into the center. The LS500 case (panel e) shows a delayed onset and a more diffuse growth trajectory. With the emission perimeter located far from the center, particles must travel longer distances before arrival; many have already grown beyond the nucleation mode during transport, resulting in a relative scarcity of sub-3 nm particles at the observation location. Although this separation is less than 1 km, a scale that conventional 0D models typically assume to be environmentally homogeneous, the results here show that even over such short distances, spatial variations in wind and vapor fields can significantly alter the banana shape.

Overall, the 3D results demonstrate that identical precursor chemistry can yield markedly different banana morphologies depending on source geometry and flow structure. The spatial heterogeneity introduced by 3D transport influences both the onset time and the growth trajectory of the nucleation mode, showing that these features are controlled not only by gas-phase chemistry and nucleation mechanisms but also by microscale environmental context, including flow-driven dilution, convergence, and localized vapor retention. Consequently, relying solely on banana plot morphology to infer NPF mechanisms or classify event types may be misleading, as local transport and mixing can substantially reshape observed size distribution patterns and apparent growth rates.

Figure 7: Time evolution of size-resolved aerosol number distributions ($dN/d \log D_p$) at the central grid point (30 m height) for the four 3D emission cases and the 0D reference model in varying colours. Each panel corresponds to a 2-hour time interval over the 24-hour simulation. Number concentrations are shown on a logarithmic scale to highlight both nucleation and accumulation modes.

Figure 7 shows the time evolution of size-resolved aerosol number distributions ($dN/d \log D_p$) at the central grid point (30 m height) for the four 3D emission geometries and the 0D reference model, in successive 2-hour intervals. This figure complements the banana plot in Figure 6 by illustrating, in discrete time slices, how particle formation and growth progress and how the mode structure changes in each scenario.

Differences between the 3D and 0D results emerge rapidly. In the 0–4 h period, all 3D cases already display a distinct nucleation mode, while the 0D model shows little to no new particle formation. By 8–12 h, the modal diameter in the 3D simulations shifts into the 10–30 nm range, whereas the 0D case remains dominated by particles smaller than 10 nm. This reflects the role of spatial transport in supplying vapor to the observation point and sustaining growth beyond the nucleation mode.

At 20–22 h, the PS case exhibits a second nucleation episode, visible as a fresh sub-10 nm mode, coinciding with a reduction in the local condensation sink. This occurs because large particles from the first event are advected away from the center, as seen in the reduction of large-particle concentrations in preceding panels. The resulting sink reduction allows vapors

to accumulate and trigger renewed NPF. Such effects are absent in the 0D model, where particles remain co-located with vapor and the condensation sink stays elevated.

While the overall timing of growth is broadly similar across 3D emission geometries, mode shapes and widths differ. The LS500 case, for example, shows delayed growth and broader distributions due to the longer transport distance from the source, while LS200 and LS300 produce sharper peaks and narrower modes during early growth phases. These differences highlight how emission geometry interacts with evolving wind fields to shape local particle size distributions.

The time-resolved size distribution confirms that the 3D framework captures variability in mode structure and timing that the 0D model cannot reproduce. Even over short distances (less than 1 km), transport and environmental heterogeneity substantially alter local particle distributions, challenging the assumption of spatial homogeneity underlying conventional box-model interpretations of NPF.

Figure 8: Size-resolved mean particle growth rates (GR, in nm hr^{-1}) for the four 3D emission scenarios (PS, LS200, LS300, LS500) and the 0D reference model, across seven diameter bins: 1–3, 3–10, 10–25, 25–40, 40–60, 60–100, and >100 nm. Marked regions (a–c) highlight diameter ranges where the 3D and 0D model results diverge most strongly. Root mean square error (RMSE) between all 3D cases and the 0D model are shown in the Appendix.

Figure 8 shows the size-resolved mean particle growth rates (GR) for each of the four 3D emission scenarios and the 0D reference model. Across all cases, GR increases with particle size up to the 25–40 nm range, consistent with atmospheric observations and theoretical expectations²⁷. The 3D simulations reproduce this trend across emission geometries and maintain substantial growth into the accumulation mode (40–100 nm), whereas the 0D model levels off beyond ~ 40 nm, failing to capture realistic large-particle growth.

The size ranges labelled a–c in Fig. 8 highlight size bins where the 3D and 0D results diverge most strongly. In region a (3–10 nm), the 0D model predicts higher GR than most 3D cases, likely reflecting its smooth, continuous nucleation trajectory (cf. Fig. 6a) that lacks localized vapor depletion. In contrast, the 3D cases show lower GR in this range, consistent with rapid particle growth out of this bin during localized vapor surges or loss to nearby condensation sinks. The absolute percentage errors in Table S5.1 in the Supporting

Information confirm that discrepancies between 3D and 0D in this range can be substantial for certain geometries (e.g., 92% for PS), but the aggregated root mean square error (RMSE), across all cases remains modest at 7.5% (Table S5.1).

In regions b (10–25 nm) and c (25–40 nm), the pattern reverses, where all 3D cases exceed the 0D GR, indicating that spatial transport sustains elevated vapor concentrations and accelerates growth through these size ranges. The magnitude of this enhancement depends strongly on source geometry, with absolute percentage errors ranging from $\sim 7\%$ to over 50% in region b, and exceeding 700% in region c for some cases. The RMSE values in Table S5.1 show that the average mismatch between 3D and 0D is negligible in region b (3.9%) but becomes pronounced in region c (37.6%), underscoring the critical role of spatially resolved flow in driving intermediate-size growth.

These results demonstrate that box-model assumptions can misrepresent both the early and intermediate stages of particle growth. In particular, neglecting the heterogeneity in vapor transport and dilution can lead to underprediction of growth in the accumulation mode and overprediction in the smallest size ranges, resulting in average discrepancies of up to 37% in growth rate estimates.

Implications

Our results demonstrate that meter-scale environmental structure strongly modulates when and where atmospheric new particle formation occurs, and how newly formed particles grow under realistic urban meteorological conditions. Even weak background winds generate substantial spatial heterogeneity in vapor convergence, dilution, and particle sinks, producing large variations in nucleation intensity, local growth rates, and the morphology of observed size distributions. These flow-driven effects provide a physical explanation for part of the long-standing early-growth discrepancy that is often attributed solely to missing chemical pathways.

Comparisons with zero-dimensional box-model representations show that assuming spa-

tial homogeneity can lead to large errors in growth-rate estimates and misinterpretation of banana-plot features. Multimodal growth, intermittent nucleation suppression, and shifting size-distribution structures emerge not only from chemistry but also from the three-dimensional organization of the urban atmosphere. These findings indicate that interpreting field observations or constraining NPF mechanisms requires explicit consideration of environmental heterogeneity at scales of tens of meters.

While this study focuses on sulfuric-acid–base nucleation, real urban settings involve additional precursors, including organics, amines, iodine species, and nitric acid, that may further interact with spatial transport. Extending 3D-resolved modeling frameworks to incorporate these pathways will be crucial for improving predictions of urban aerosol evolution, exposure, and climate-relevant particle populations.

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Supporting Information Available

The Supporting Information provides full mathematical formulations of the Air3D, AM-Chem, and Aero3D modules; input parameters; and supplementary figures and tables. All simulation data and analysis scripts underlying the figures in this study are available via a public Zenodo repository (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17036552). The model code is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

References

- (1) Zhang, R.; Khalizov, A.; Wang, L.; Hu, M.; Xu, W. Nucleation and Growth of Nanoparticles in the Atmosphere. *Chemical Reviews* **2012**, *112*, 1957–2011, PMID: 22044487.
- (2) Gordon, H. et al. Causes and importance of new particle formation in the present-day and preindustrial atmospheres. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* **2017**, *122*, 8739–8760.
- (3) Zhao, B. et al. Global variability in atmospheric new particle formation mechanisms. *Nature* **2024**, *631*, 98–105.
- (4) Brean, J.; Rowell, A.; Beddows, D. C. S.; Shi, Z.; Harrison, R. M. Estimates of Future New Particle Formation under Different Emission Scenarios in Beijing. *Environmental Science & Technology* **2023**, *57*, 4741–4750, PMID: 36930743.
- (5) Su, P.; Joutsensaari, J.; Dada, L.; Zaidan, M. A.; Nieminen, T.; Li, X.; Wu, Y.; Decesari, S.; Tarkoma, S.; Petäjä, T.; Kulmala, M.; Pellikka, P. New particle formation event detection with Mask R-CNN. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* **2022**, *22*, 1293–1309.
- (6) Mishra, S. et al. Rapid night-time nanoparticle growth in Delhi driven by biomass-burning emissions. *Nature Geoscience* **2023**, *16*, 224–230.
- (7) Lee, S.-H.; Gordon, H.; Yu, H.; Lehtipalo, K.; Haley, R.; Li, Y.; Zhang, R. New Particle Formation in the Atmosphere: From Molecular Clusters to Global Climate. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* **2019**, *124*, 7098–7146.
- (8) Yao, L. et al. Atmospheric new particle formation from sulfuric acid and amines in a Chinese megacity. *Science* **2018**, *361*, 278–281.
- (9) Cai, R. et al. Sulfuric acid–amine nucleation in urban Beijing. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* **2021**, *21*, 2457–2468.

- (10) Baccharini, A.; Karlsson, L.; Dommen, J.; Duplessis, P.; Vüllers, J.; Brooks, I. M.; Saiz-Lopez, A.; Salter, M.; Tjernström, M.; Baltensperger, U.; Zieger, P.; Schmale, J. Frequent new particle formation over the high Arctic pack ice by enhanced iodine emissions. *Nature Communications* **2020**, *11*, 4924.
- (11) Bianchi, F. et al. New particle formation in the free troposphere: A question of chemistry and timing. *Science* **2016**, *352*, 1109–1112.
- (12) Kecorius, S. et al. Atmospheric new particle formation identifier using longitudinal global particle number size distribution data. *Scientific Data* **2024**, *11*, 1239.
- (13) Salma, I.; Weidinger, T.; Rohonczy, J.; Vörösmarty, M. Types of regional and localised new aerosol particle formation and growth processes: Atmospheric Banana Atlas. *npj Climate and Atmospheric Science* **2025**, *8*, 261.
- (14) Sellar, A. A. et al. UKESM1: Description and Evaluation of the U.K. Earth System Model. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems* **2019**, *11*, 4513–4558.
- (15) Mulcahy, J. P. et al. Description and evaluation of aerosol in UKESM1 and HadGEM3-GC3.1 CMIP6 historical simulations. *Geoscientific Model Development* **2020**, *13*, 6383–6423.
- (16) O’Meara, S. P.; Xu, S.; Topping, D.; Alfarra, M. R.; Capes, G.; Lowe, D.; Shao, Y.; McFiggans, G. PyCHAM (v2.1.1): a Python box model for simulating aerosol chambers. *Geoscientific Model Development* **2021**, *14*, 675–702.
- (17) Tian, J.; Brem, B. T.; West, M.; Bond, T. C.; Rood, M. J.; Riemer, N. Simulating aerosol chamber experiments with the particle-resolved aerosol model PartMC. *Aerosol Science and Technology* **2017**, *51*, 856–867.
- (18) Kivekäs, N.; Carpman, J.; Roldin, P.; Leppä, J.; O’Connor, E.; Kristensson, A.; Asmi, E. Coupling an aerosol box model with one-dimensional flow: a tool for un-

- derstanding observations of new particle formation events. *Tellus B: Chemical and Physical Meteorology* **2016**, *68*, 29706.
- (19) Ghosh, K.; Tripathi, S. N.; Joshi, M.; Mayya, Y. S.; Khan, A.; Sapra, B. K. Particle formation from vapors emitted from glowing wires: Theory and experiments. *Aerosol Science and Technology* **2020**, *54*, 243–261.
- (20) Vohra, K.; Ghosh, K.; Tripathi, S.; Thangamani, I.; Goyal, P.; Dutta, A.; Verma, V. Submicron particle dynamics for different surfaces under quiescent and turbulent conditions. *Atmospheric Environment* **2017**, *152*, 330–344.
- (21) Laakso, L.; Mäkelä, J. M.; Pirjola, L.; Kulmala, M. Model studies on ion-induced nucleation in the atmosphere. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* **2002**, *107*, AAC 5–1–AAC 5–19.
- (22) Ghosh, K.; Tripathi, S.; Joshi, M.; Mayya, Y.; Khan, A.; Sapra, B. Modeling studies on coagulation of charged particles and comparison with experiments. *Journal of Aerosol Science* **2017**, *105*, 35–47.
- (23) Baik, J.-J.; Kang, Y.-S.; Kim, J.-J. Modeling reactive pollutant dispersion in an urban street canyon. *Atmospheric Environment* **2007**, *41*, 934–949.
- (24) Cai, R.; Yan, C.; Worsnop, D. R.; Bianchi, F.; Kerminen, V.-M.; Liu, Y.; Wang, L.; Zheng, J.; Kulmala, M.; Jiang, J. An indicator for sulfuric acid–amine nucleation in atmospheric environments. *Aerosol Science and Technology* **2021**, *55*, 1059–1069.
- (25) Stolzenburg, D. et al. Incomplete mass closure in atmospheric nanoparticle growth. *npj Climate and Atmospheric Science* **2025**, *8*, 75.
- (26) Quéléver, L. L. J.; Dada, L.; Asmi, E.; Lampilahti, J.; Chan, T.; Ferrara, J. E.; Copes, G. E.; Pérez-Fogwill, G.; Barreira, L.; Aurela, M.; Worsnop, D. R.; Jokinen, T.; Sipilä, M. Investigation of new particle formation mechanisms and aerosol processes

at Marambio Station, Antarctic Peninsula. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* **2022**, *22*, 8417–8437.

- (27) Kulmala, M. et al. Direct Observations of Atmospheric Aerosol Nucleation. *Science* **2013**, *339*, 943–946.

TOC Graphic

